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Historical Sciences

THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM IN THE USSR IN 1960-1990

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Abstract

The article discusses the development of tourism activities in the USSR in 1960-1990. It is shown that at the turn of the 80-90-s of the XX century, socio-economic and political factors did not contribute to the full and balanced development of Russian tourism. Since the beginning of the 1990-s, due to geopolitical tensions within the CIS countries and Russia itself, the tourist recreational space has been invariably shrinking, many vast regions simply fell out of the tourist and recreational sphere. At the same time, the financing of tourism by the state and trade unions was significantly reduced. And the surviving tourist establishments set high prices, which was not always accompanied by an improvement in the quality and quantity of services provided. As a result, the demand for domestic travel and leisure, which used to dominate before, declined sharply, and the demand for trips abroad increased just as sharply.

Keywords: tourism, temple, travel, history, country, society.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the early 1960s in the USSR, there was an increase in tourism activities. In 1962, a system of tourism councils was created, which was managed by the Central Council for Tourism of the All-Union Central Council of Trade Unions. By 1965, tourism councils were organized in all the Union republics and most of the autonomous republics, territories and regions, which developed and mastered new routes. Tourist travel has become one of the most popular forms of recreation for Soviet citizens. The development of planned tourist trips was carried out by the Central Council for Tourism and Excursions. The Central Council begins to issue vouchers for routes that have the status of all-Union. All other routes, which were under the jurisdiction of the republican, regional and regional councils for tourism and excursions, belonged to the local ones. In the 60s. tourist and excursion organizations of trade unions have developed over 13 thousand routes: linear, ring, radial. All-Union and local routes covered the whole country and made it possible to get acquainted with the most interesting cities and sights of the Soviet Union. Therefore, the experience of the historical evolution of domestic tourism is extremely necessary for the organizers and workers of the tourism industry, as it will reveal certain patterns in the process of tourism development and outline ways to further improve activities.

The relevance of the study is also determined by the lack of scientific development of the problems of tourism development in Russia in the historical aspect.

II. METHODOLOGY

The principles of historicism and objectivity became the theoretical basis of the study. During its implementation, a system of methods typical for the humanities, as well as specific ones, which are used in historiographical and interdisciplinary works, was used. The system included the following methods: comparative-historical, systemic, problem-chronological, historical reconstruction, retrospective. The use of historical-comparative and retrospective methods allowed the author to reveal the multifaceted nature of the tourism phenomenon. The historical-comparative method of research made it possible to analyze the statistical data of the general patterns and features of the development of tourism in Russia, to identify the reasons that both contribute to the development of tourism and hinder this process.

These research methods make it possible to ensure the completeness of the factual description, to determine the role and place of tourism in the space of mass culture.

III. RESULTS

In the Soviet Union, tourism has become a full-fledged ideological machine, the authors of which were prominent state and party figures of the country (A.V. Lunacharsky, N.K. Krupskaya, N.I. Bukharin), and the essence, which was subordination of travel and excursions to political and ideological tasks.

An analysis of the activities of the state in the field of tourism showed that there was no clear concept in this matter in the early years of Soviet power. The main tasks that were set for tourism in the 1920s. were: educational, educational, health-improving, propaganda of the ideas of socialism, building a new anti-religious picture of the world. The solution of these tasks was to create a basis for the formation of a nationwide communist ideology. Tourism of the Soviet period developed spontaneously, various structures were engaged in it, for this reason, ideas about the tasks and goals of tourism and about tourism as a type of activity varied greatly. So, some saw tourism only as educational excursions, while others considered it one of the elements of physical culture, there were also those who represented tourism as pleasure walks on a weekend or during a vacation, as an acquaintance with their native land or local history, and, nevertheless, they were united by the common opinion that tourism should carry the ideology of socialism. Tourism acted not only as a collective propagandist and agitator, but also as a collective organizer and controller. Tourism had the ability to irresistibly beckon and attract with the brilliance of novelty - a previously unseen way of life, new ideas, new relationships between comrades on the campaign. He awakened a desire for another life, called to turn the page, to cross out everything that was before; promised comradesly help and support in the implementation of this seemingly simple step - to join the general movement of the young, beautiful, healthy and cheerful majority towards some unknown, but definitely bright future. From the 1950s to the 1970s in the USSR, the ideological side of tourism began to flow into the social. Thus, social tourism begins to develop. Within the framework of social tourism, domestic travel is of decisive importance. As of 1985, in the Soviet Union, the number of tourists making domestic trips was 15 times higher than the number of tourists going abroad. A similar situation persisted until the early 1990s, when the destruction of the state monopoly in the tourism sector marked the beginning of a radical transformation in this industry. One of the results is the inactivity of over 10 thousand objects of social tourism. In 1975, radial tourist routes were developed for families with seven-year-old children, passing through special camp sites, and weekend routes. Since the beginning of the 1970s, the tourist-excursion rest of parents with children has been closely intertwined with the treatment of working families in health resorts - also a relatively new type of organization of family vacations.

The first health resorts for this purpose with a total capacity of 25,000 people were established in 1972; by the beginning of the eleventh five-year plan, the number of seats had already increased to 124,000. Families vacationing in them widely used the services of local tourist and excursion institutions that provide services to parents with children. A great merit in the development and formation of the tourist-excursion business in the country, in the coverage and generalization of best practices belonged to the journal "Tourist".

In the anniversary - hundredth April issue of the magazine for 1974, the editors of the journal addressed their readers:

"You are holding in your hands the spring, April hundredth issue of the Tourist journal. "Fatherland - this is the main theme of the magazine, in touristic terms - the main route" - we wrote in the first issue of the new monthly. The number of excursion routes and transport trips has increased several times. Outdoor enthusiasts have a huge choice that they could only dream of eight years ago. Today, a dense network of routes, developed by tourist and excursion organizations of trade unions, stretches from the shores of the Baltic to the volcanoes of Kamchatka and from the sands of Turkmenistan to the ice of Svalbard. Like an avalanche in the mountains, the flow of various information, interesting and useful for the traveler, is growing. Under these conditions, the monthly journal faces new responsible and complex tasks. On the pages of "Tourist" readers get acquainted with new tourist bases and hotels, routes, learn about new equipment, receive information about rallies and competitions, and much more! Important changes in the structure of tourism management were made in 1976, when the governing bodies for types of tourism operating under the councils for tourism and excursions - central, republican, regional, regional and city sections merged into a single public body - the federation of tourism.

The management structure of the amateur tourist movement included: tourism sections (Tourist Clubs), physical education teams of enterprises, institutions, educational institutions, collective farms and state farms, district, city tourist clubs of the Councils for Tourism and Excursions of the All-Union Central Council of Trade Unions. Model regulations on the Club of tourists of an enterprise, institution, educational institution, on the city (district) tourist club of the Council for Tourism and Excursions were approved. Hiking is one of the mass types of amateur travel. More than three and a half million people gave their leisure time to him in the USSR.

Kislovodsk. This resort of the Caucasus is known to all. These are majestic mountains, unique nature, warm climate, healthy air and a huge amount of different "living water" - mineral springs of Narzan.

In the 1980s, the improvement of the tourism system continued. In this regard, the Congress of Trade Unions of the country gave a specific instruction to the councils and committees of trade unions: "... To develop in every possible way the tourism and excursion business in the country, as an important means of educating workers and strengthening their health, to raise the level of service for tourists, to improve the types and forms of services provided to the population. To make wider use of tourist trips and excursions as an encouragement for the best production workers and winners of socialist competition, for the recreation of working and studying youth, during vacations, vacations and weekends.

In the first half of the 1980s, Soviet trade unions did a lot to create conditions for the successful long-term development of the tourist and excursion business. The basis of the General scheme for its improvement for the period up to 1990 was laid. This included a powerful re-equipment of the material and technical base, and further structural expansion of the network of tourist and excursion institutions, and training of personnel, as well as increasing the efficiency of tourism and excursions.

Boarding house "Svetlana". Sochi 1980.

The trade unions turned to tourism as one of the opportunities to make the leisure time of the Soviet people not only varied and interesting, but also socially useful. The industry was tasked with building tourist facilities for 80 thousand places in the eleventh five-year plan. 550 million capital investments were allocated for these purposes.

Let us turn to the growth dynamics of the tourism industry in the country. In the early 70s, Soviet trade unions had more than 500 tourist bases for 114,000 places, 6,765 tourist and health camps, 220 fishermen and hunters' houses, 8,275 good equipment rentals, and many tourist clubs. There were more than 75,000 tourist sections, uniting about 5 million people, at enterprises, institutions and educational institutions attached to physical education groups, and more than 200,000 public tourist personnel were trained. From the 90s of the XX century until today, tourism has become an independent type of business. Against the backdrop of a deep structural economic crisis in the country that began in the early 1990s, tourism developed dynamically, while undergoing tremendous changes. Instead of a system of budget financing and centralized distribution of tourist vouchers, a market tourism industry was created, which combines various forms of entrepreneurial activity - joint-stock companies, limited liability companies, and individual private entrepreneurship.

The activation of international tourism was facilitated by changes in the state structure of our country, economic and political transformations, "commitment to the pan-European priorities of individual rights and freedoms and, in particular, the right to free movement, liberalization and simplification of tourist formalities - all this contributed to the activation of tourist flows, both entry, and outbound." According to Rosstat, the entry of foreign tourists into Russia during the first 6 months of 1990 decreased by 14.2% compared with the data for the first half of 1989, when the inbound tourist flow suddenly grew by 9.8%.

The collapse of the USSR led to the collapse of a unified system of tourist and excursion services for the population. The article "tourism" disappears from the state budget. If previously centralized financing supported the tourism infrastructure, determined relatively low prices for tourist and hotel services, then its absence led to the actual decline of the hotel industry. A large number of tourist-excursion, sanatorium-resort and hotel establishments and complexes of the country were redesigned or fell into disrepair due to dilapidated condition.

In a spontaneously developing market, many travel companies and hotels declare themselves bankrupt. The decline in living standards of the population, rising prices have led to a reduction in demand for tourist services. For these reasons, the system of domestic tourism is practically falling apart, all-Union and republican routes that were popular with the population cease to exist.

Inbound tourism in the 1990s is also going through hard times. In the late 80s and early 90s, foreigners began to treat Russia with apprehension due to the growth of crime in the country, its political and financial instability.

An important role in the fall of interest in the country was played by the lack of new offers in the tourist market, new tourist routes, comfortable hotels, insufficient level of service, etc. There is a restructuring of tourist flows of foreigners visiting us. If earlier most tourists came to Russia from the countries of the former Socialist Commonwealth, then in the 90s people from the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS) were drawn to Russia. At the same time, the percentage of those arriving in the country is significantly increasing due to immigrants who, under the pretext of tourist travel, crossed the borders. This factor corrected the statistics for outbound tourism as well.

IV. CONCLUSION

Of course, beyond the scope of this historical study were issues of a highly specialized nature related to the functioning of the tourism industry and, in particular, the production and use of tourist equipment, the methodology for compiling routes, calculating their cost, etc. After all, the development of the above and related problems not only goes beyond goals, but also lies outside the plane of the actual historical article. Which, however, does not negate the importance of such studies, including in terms of studying the historical experience of such activities.

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РАЗВИТИЕ ТУРИЗМА В СССР В 1960-1990 ГОДЫ

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Аннотация

В статье рассматривается развитие туристической деятельности в СССР в 1960-1990 годах. Показано, что на рубеже 80-90-х годов XX века социально-экономические и политические факторы не способствовали полноценному и сбалансированному развитию российского туризма. С начала 1990-х годов из-за геополитической напряженности внутри стран СНГ и самой России туристско-рекреационное пространство неизменно сокращалось, многие обширные регионы просто выпали из туристско-рекреационной сферы. В то же время финансирование туризма государством и профсоюзами было значительно сокращено. А уцелевшие туристические заведения устанавливали высокие цены, что не всегда сопровождалось улучшением качества и количества предоставляемых услуг. В результате спрос на внутренние путешествия и отдых, который раньше доминировал, резко снизился, а спрос на поездки за границу резко возрос.

Ключевые слова: туризм, храм, путешествие, история, страна, общество.

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